

Valid Publication of 22 Nothogenera and Two New Combinations in Bromeliaceae

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER¹

Abstract—Valid publication of the nothogeneric names *×Barvriesea*, *×Billya*, *×Forzzanthus*, *×Forzzautskyia*, *×Guzgoudaea*, *×Guzlutheria*, *×Hohenquesmea*, *×Luthandsia*, *×Nidusincoraea*, *×Orthocohnia*, *×Rokautanthus*, *×Rokautsincoraea*, *×Sincoraechmea*, *×Sincoregelia*, *×Sincorglaziovia*, *×Sincorphytum*, *×Sincortanthus*, *×Vriesgoudaea*, *×Vrieslutheria*, *×Wallandsia*, *×Wallfussia* and *×Zizkagoudaea*, and two new combinations, *×Guzlutheria magnifica* and *×Sincoregelia lymanii* (Bromeliaceae).

21 nothogeneric names listed in the online Bromeliad Cultivar Register² were never validly published. These names and a 22nd name, *×Forzzautskyia*, are validated here. Additionally, the new combinations *×Guzlutheria magnifica* and *×Sincoregelia lymanii* are proposed.

***×Barvriesea* Lawn³ nothogen. nov.**

Barfussia J.Manzanares & W.Till *×Vriesea* Lindley

***×Billya* Bethmann[?]⁴ nothogen. nov.**

Billbergia Thunb. *×Puya* Molina

***×Forzzanthus* Lawn⁵ nothogen. nov.**

Cryptanthus Otto & A.Dietr. *×Forzzaea* Leme, S.Heller & Zizka

***×Forzzautskyia* NN⁶ nothogen. nov.**

Forzzaea Leme, S.Heller & Zizka *×Rokautskyia* Leme, S.Heller & Zizka

¹ Roggekamp 379
NL-2592 VV Den Haag
m@vdm.nu

² <https://www.bsi.org/registry/>

³ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xBARVRIESE&id=14257#14257>

⁴ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xBILLYA&id=12406#12406>

⁵ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xFORZZANTHUS&id=14273#14273>

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×*Guzgoudaea* Lawn⁷ **nothogen. nov.**

Goudaea W.Till & Barfuss × *Guzmania* Ruiz & Pavon

×*Guzlutheria* Lawn⁸ **nothogen. nov.**

Guzmania Ruiz & Pavon × *Lutheria* Barfuss & W.Till

×*Guzlutheria magnifica* (Carrière) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

Guzmania zahnii (H.J.Veitch) Mez × *Lutheria splendens* (Brongn.) Barfuss & W.Till

≡ *Tillandsia zahnii* var. *magnifica* Carrière

Rev. Hort. [Paris]. 55: 62 (1883)

≡ *Tillandsia* × *magnifica* (Carrière) Mottet

Dict. Prat. Hort. 5: 274 (1899)

≡ ×*Guzvriesea magnifica* (Carrière) M.B.Foster

Bull. Bromeliad Soc. 13(4): 85 (1963)

Note: *Tillandsia zahnii* is usually cited as ‘Hort.Veitch ex Hook.f. – Bot. Mag. 99: sub t. 6059 (1873)’, but the name is mentioned only as a synonym there. It was validly published in Gard. Chron. 1874: 531.

×*Hohenquesmea* Lawn⁹ **nothogen. nov.**

Aechmea Ruiz & Pav. × *Hohenbergia* Schult. & Schult.f. in Roem. & Schult. × *Quesnelia* Gaudich.

×*Luthandsia* Lawn¹⁰ **nothogen. nov.**

Lutheria Barfuss & W.Till × *Tillandsia* L.

×*Nidusincoraea* Lawn¹¹ **nothogen. nov.**

Nidularium Lem. × *Sincoraea* Ule

×*Orthocohnia* Lawn¹² **nothogen. nov.**

Deuterocohnia Mez × *Orthophytum* Beer

⁷ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xGUZGOUDAEA&id=14255#14255>

⁸ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xGUZLUTHERIA&id=14258#14258>

⁹ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xHOHENQUESMEA&id=14675#14675>

¹⁰ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xLUTHANDSIA&id=14259#14259>

¹¹ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xNIDUSINCORAEA&id=14267#14267>

¹² <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xORTHOCHOHNIA&id=13060#13060>

×**Rokautanthus** Lawn¹³ **nothogen. nov.**

Rokautskyia Leme, S.Heller & Zizka × *Cryptanthus* Otto & A.Dietr.

×**Rokautsincoraea** Lawn¹⁴ **nothogen. nov.**

Rokautskyia Leme, S.Heller & Zizka × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Sincoraechmea** Lawn¹⁵ **nothogen. nov.**

Aechmea Ruiz & Pavon × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Sincoregelia** Lawn¹⁶ **nothogen. nov.**

Neoregelia L.B.Smith × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Sincoregelia lymanii** (M.B.Foster) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

Neoregelia bahiana (Ule) L.B.Sm. × *Sincoraea navioides* (L.B.Sm.) Louzada & Wand.

≡ ×*Neophytum lymanii* M.B.Foster

Bull. Bromeliad Soc. 8(5): 73 (1958)

×**Sincorglaziovia** Lawn¹⁷ **nothogen. nov.**

Neoglaziovia Mez × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Sincorphytum** Lawn¹⁸ **nothogen. nov.**

Orthophytum Beer × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Sincortanthus** Lawn¹⁹ **nothogen. nov.**

Cryptanthus Otto & A.Dietr. × *Sincoraea* Ule

×**Vriesgoudaea** Lawn²⁰ **nothogen. nov.**

Goudaea W.Till & Barfuss × *Vriesea* Lindley

¹³ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xROKAUTANTHUS&id=14274#14274>

¹⁴ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xROKAUTSINCORAEA&id=14272#14272>

¹⁵ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xSINCORAECHMEA&id=14268#14268>

¹⁶ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xSINCOREGELIA&id=14263#14263>

¹⁷ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xSINCORGLAZIOVIA&id=14266#14266>

¹⁸ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xSINCORPHYTUM&id=14264#14264>

¹⁹ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xSINCORTANTHUS&id=14265#14265>

²⁰ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xVRIESGOUDAEA&id=14254#14254>

×*Vriesslutheria* Lawn²¹ **nothogen. nov.**

Lutheria Barfuss & W.Till × *Vriesea* Lindley

×*Wallandsia* Lawn²² **nothogen. nov.**

Tillandsia L. × *Wallisia* É.Morren

×*Wallfussia* Lawn²³ **nothogen. nov.**

Barfussia J.Manzanares & W.Till × *Wallisia* É.Morren

×*Zizkagoudaea* Lawn²⁴ **nothogen. nov.**

Goudaea W.Till & Barfuss × *Zizkaea* W.Till & Barfuss

×*Vriesslutheria* ‘Hunua Cherry Crumpet’
John Mitchell

×*Sincoregelia* ‘Orgulho’
Paulo Tosta

²¹ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xVRIESLUTHERIA&id=14256#14256>

²² <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xWALLANDSIA&id=14260#14260>

²³ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xWALLFUSSIA&id=14261#14261>

²⁴ <https://www.bsi.org/registry/?genus=xZIZKAGOUDAEA&id=14262#14262>

×*Zizkagoudaea* 'Babylon'
Ross Draper

×*Vriesgoudaea* 'Jags Hunua Autumn'
John Mitchell

×*Hohenquesmea* 'Valley Hoodoo'
Aaron Smythe